

Targeting ischemic penumbra Part II: selective drug delivery using liposome technologies

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Abstract

In the present review (part II), we discuss the challenges and promises of selective drug delivery to ischemic brain tissue by liposome technologies. In part I of this serial review, we proposed “selective drug delivery to ischemic brain tissue” as a technique for neuroprotective treatment of acute ischemic stroke. To be effective, drugs must pass a series of barriers to arrive at ischemic brain. Brain ischemia results in metabolic and structural changes in the ischemic region, which cause additional obstacles for drug delivery. Liposome drug delivery system can pass these barriers and selectively target ischemic tissue by utilizing ischemia-induced changes in metabolism and molecular structure.

Keywords: Penumbra; drug delivery; liposome; pH-sensitive; blood-brain barrier.

Acute ischemic stroke causes irreversible injury in the ischemic core, but reversible injury in the peri-focal zone, the penumbra. (Astrup et al. 1981; Ebinger et al. 2009; Memezawa et al. 1992) Conventional drug delivery methods cause unwanted drug exposure to other tissue or brain regions. Because of limited blood supply to ischemic penumbra region, systemic high dose is often required for a drug to reach therapeutic levels in ischemic tissue, which may cause severe side effects and toxicity. Advanced drug delivery system using liposome techniques may achieve effective regional drug level without increasing systemic dose. Liposomal nanocarriers facilitate penetration of biological membrane, protect drugs from enzymatic and chemical degradation and albumin binding, and minimize drug exposures to non-target tissue. (Jain 2007; Tiwari and Amiji 2006) Following paragraphs discuss the challenges of selective drug delivery to ischemic brain tissue and the promises of liposome technologies in stroke therapy.

1. The blood brain-barrier

The blood brain barrier (BBB) consists of an endothelial enclosure and periendothelial accessories, which include pericytes, astrocytes, and a basal membrane. BBB strictly limits exchanges of sub-

stance between blood and the brain. The endothelial cells of the BBB lack fenestrations and have both tight junctions and adherens junctions between the cells (Bazzoni and Dejana 2004; Kniessel and Wolburg 2000; Schulze and Firth 1993). BBB prevents passive diffusion of hydrophilic molecules and allows diffusion of uncharged small molecules (Grieb et al. 1985; Levin 1980). A thin basement membrane (i.e. basal lamina) surrounds the endothelial cells and pericytes supporting the abluminal surface of the endothelium. Astrocytes further encase this structure with endfeet interspersed with pericytes. (Hellstrom et al. 2001; Kacem et al. 1998). The BBB protects brain from foreign substance, but it also strictly limits therapeutic agents entering the brain.

Because of the lipidic nature of all biological membranes, including brain endothelial cell membrane, lipophilic molecules can diffuse across BBB whilst hydrophilic molecules utilize transporter-facilitated systems. (Pardridge 1999) Active transport of some endogenous or exogenous hydrophilic molecules crossing BBB can be in either influx or efflux directions. (Ohtsuki and Terasaki 2007) Some of these transporters, such as for amino acids, monocarboxylic acids, organic cations, hexoses, nucleosides, peptides, have been well studied and molecularly identi-

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fied. We refer the reader to the excellent review articles (Tamai and Tsuji 2000; Tsuji 2005) for more information of transport- assisted passage of BBB.

BBB during cerebral ischemia

Cerebral ischemia causes BBB damage and temporary BBB disruption. However, this temporary BBB opening causes edema, hemorrhagic transformation, and additional brain injury, therefore, it cannot be used for neuroprotective purpose. The area of the BBB disruption depends on injury intensity, injury type, and presence or absence of reperfusion. The BBB opening during ischemia in the absence of reperfusion occurs when the ischemic damage is already irreversible. For example, gadolinium-diethylenetriamine penta-acetic acid (Gd-DTPA) extravasations was found grossly visible between 4.5 and 6 h after permanent MCAO (Kastrup et al. 1999). At this time, ischemic brain injury has already happened and is mostly irreversible. Reperfusion induced BBB disruption occurs after 3 and 48 hours of 2-h MCAO with reperfusion, with maximal opening at 48 hours and returns to normal by 14 days (Rosenberg et al. 1998). Gelatinase A (MMP-2) and TIMP-2 are associated with reperfusion induced BBB disruption (Rosenberg et al. 1998). After transient 20-min MCAO BBB disruption peaks at day 7 and resolves at day 14 after ischemia (Abulrob et al. 2008). BBB disruption during reperfusion stage is believed to be a precursor to hemorrhagic transformation (HT) and poor outcome (Latour et al. 2004), which should be treated with adjunctive therapies.

Methods for transducing the blood-brain barrier

Traditional methods for opening BBB are invasive, inefficient, and non-selective. Transient osmotic opening of the BBB by arabinose or mannitol (Shinohara et al. 1979; Siegal et al. 2000), shunts (Zlotnik et al. 2008), or implanting microspheres (Beduneau et al. 2007; Emerich et al. 1999) to deliver therapeutic agents are invasive methods and have potential side-effects. Osmotic agents can cause accumulation of mannitol in the cerebral tissue and increase edema, whilst implantations require surgery (Kaufmann and Cardoso 1992; Maioriello et al. 2002). These methods do not selectively open BBB for drug delivery or selectively target tissue.

More advanced methods for CNS drug delivery include altering the molecular structure of drugs to increase their membrane permeability, fusing the drug molecule with cell penetrating peptides, and encapsulating drugs into liposomal nanocarriers. Drugs can also compete to use a carrier system if their structure mimics that of an endogenous molecule. Drugs that cannot use an endogenous transport system may be fused to a molecule, such as transferrin or glucose (Rajkumar et al. 1995), which can be effectively

transported across the BBB. In addition, monoclonal antibodies can be utilized to transport some drugs across the BBB via a receptor-mediated transport system (Lee et al. 2000; Pardridge 2005). In a similar manner, many cell penetrating peptides (CPPs) have been used for CNS drug delivery by conjugating to functioning therapeutic agents for cerebral ischemia (Esneault et al. 2008; Eum et al. 2004; Fan et al. 2006). Nanoliposomes and other nanoparticles can be utilized to deliver genes, proteins/peptides, and many other agents across the BBB. Nanoliposomes are engineered to enclose hydrophilic or amphiphilic agents within one or two lipid bilayers, similar to biological membranes.

The nanoliposome crosses the BBB by one of three methods: passive diffusion, endocytosis, or assisted passage with brain-targeting ligands (Beduneau et al. 2007; Chen et al. 2010; Markoutsas et al. 2011; Tamaru et al. 2010; Wong et al. 2010). These advanced methods for CNS drug delivery transduce BBB for a particular therapy, but they are not readily tissue-selective or cell type-selective. It is possible to achieve significant improvements on the delivery specificity and efficiency by extensive modification and optimization of these methods. Selective BBB transduction for drug delivery that targets the diseased tissue will improve delivery efficiency and reduce adverse effect, and potentially can be used in ischemic stroke and other CNS disorders.

2. Compromised blood supply and shrinkage of extracellular space

In addition to the challenge of BBB, ischemic brain tissue also has compromised blood flow that can further limit efficient drug delivery through blood supply. For example, the regional cerebral blood flow (rCBF) in the inner penumbra is only about 15 ml/100g/min (Murphy et al. 2006; Ohashi et al. 2005). Moreover, the extracellular space (ECS) is also decreased during ischemia (Thorne and Nicholson 2006; Zoremba et al. 2008). Ischemia causes cytotoxic edema that increases cell volume by 12% and reduces ECS by 50%. (Homola et al. 2006) Theoretically, large dose will be needed for reaching an effective regional drug concentration; this increased dose may lead to severe drug toxicity. Many neuroprotectants have been tested effective in animal studies, but they cannot be used in stroke patients at effective dose because of drug-related severe toxicity.

3. The advantages of liposomal drug delivery system

Advanced technologies, such as pH-sensitive nanoliposomes with enhanced BBB penetration and tissue selectivity, hold promises for ischemic stroke therapies. The lipid layer affords nanoliposomes BBB permeability for their encapsulated contents. Moreo-

ver, these liposomal nanocarriers can acquire additional features through further modification, such as long circulating time, enhanced BBB penetration and ischemic tissue selectivity. The advantages of using nanoliposomes also include: 1). maintaining drugs in active state when being encapsulated inside the nanoliposome; 2). minimizing exposure to non-target tissue when tissue-selective liposomes being used; 3). providing a protective shell for the encapsulated contents, which prevents drugs from non-specific binding and enzymatic digestion; 4). being able to afford a high intraliposomal drug concentration. Therefore, nanoliposomes could be used as a basic means for drug delivery to ischemic stroke penumbra. (Jain 2007; Tiwari and Amiji 2006)

4. Possibility of selective drug delivery to penumbral tissue

Brain ischemia causes a metabolic shift towards anaerobic glycolysis, resulting in a lower intracellular pH in the ischemic brain tissue. Targeting at this property of ischemic brain tissue, liposomal nanocarriers may be optimized to selectively release their contents under acidic condition (Collins et al. 1989) similar to the microenvironment of ischemic brain tissue (pH<6.75) (Anderson et al. 1999). The fusogenic property of dioleoylphosphatidylethanolamine and transactivator of transcription (TAT) peptide will facilitate liposomes escaping from endosomes/lysosomes and normal cells (Boomer et al. 2009; Hatakeyama et al. 2009). These liposomes will release their cargos when they reach cytosols of ischemic cells that have a pH of around 6.75. The pH difference between extracellular and intracellular space in ischemic tissue is usually less than 0.5 unit in normoglycemic rats (Nedergaard et al. 1991), therefore, a portion of pH-sensitive liposomes will deliver their cargos in the interstitial space.

These liposomal nanocarriers can gain additional features by incorporating functional molecules onto their membrane surfaces. Stroke-homing peptide (Hong et al. 2008) may be useful for selective drug delivery to ischemic brain tissue.

5. The strategies for liposomal drug delivery to ischemic penumbra

Currently there are no specially tailored nanoliposomes available for targeting ischemic stroke penumbra. A nanosized pH-sensitive liposome commonly has 3-5 structural components, which include a basic lipid, a balancer, a stabilizer, optional function peptides, and an optional tracer. The basic lipid provides the sensitivity to acidic environment. The balancer is used to titrate pH-sensitivity to the desired level. The stabilizer protects the nanoliposome from unwanted leakage and fusion. Optional function peptides may provide the nanoliposome additional abili-

ties, such as enhanced BBB penetration and specific tissue targeting. Optional tracer can be a fluorescent lipid or fluorescent peptide.

The basic lipid DOPE

There are two basic lipids that provide nanoliposomes a sensitivity to acidic environment, the phosphatidylethanolamines (PE), and the dioleoylphosphatidylethanolamine (DOPE) (Drummond et al. 2000). PE based nanoliposomes tend to release their contents in a more acidic environment that may mimic ischemic core. DOPE based nanoliposomes can be optimized to release contents at mild acidic environment that may mimic ischemic penumbra. DOPE also has fusogenic property that facilitates liposomes escaping from endosomes and lysosomes (Boomer et al. 2009; Hatakeyama et al. 2009). The mild acidic activation and fusogenic property of DOPE plus residual blood flow in penumbral region give DOPE-based liposomes a higher chance of drug delivery to ischemic penumbra.

Balancers and stabilizers:

N-succinyldioleoylphosphatidylethanolamine (suc-DOPE), oleic acid (OA), palmitoylhomocysteine (PHC), cholesteryl hemisuccinate (CHEMS), and 1,2-dioleoyl- or 1,2-dipalmitoyl-sn-3-succinylglycerol (DOSG or DSPG) are a few of the stabilizers that have been used to prepare pH-sensitive liposome formulations. CHEMS-balanced pH-sensitive nanoliposomes have been demonstrated for efficient intracellular delivery. (Costin et al. 2002) Poly (ethylene-glycol) (PEG) with different molecular weights is the most commonly used stabilizer and compatible with pH-sensitive nanoliposomes.

PEG coated pH-sensitive nanoliposomes for long circulating time.

Conventional or plain nanoliposomes are rapidly removed from circulation by the reticuloendothelial system (RES) and accumulate in the liver and spleen (Allen 1994; Cowens et al. 1993; Rahman et al. 1990), which limits their clinical applications. Recent progress in microencapsulation showed that introducing poly(ethylene-glycol) (PEG) onto nanoliposome surface can prevent nanoliposomes from opsonization (Allen et al. 1991; Blume and Cevc 1990; Blume and Cevc 1993; Torchilin et al. 1994), resulting in a long circulating time (Klibanov et al. 1990). PEG coated pH-sensitive nanoliposomes can be constructed using low pH-cleavable PEG or DSPE-PEG of a proper molar ratio. The working mechanisms of PEGylated pH-sensitive nanoliposomes have been well illustrated. (Romberg et al. 2008; Sawant et al. 2006) The low pH-cleavable PEG is linked to its anchor by some special linkers, which include Diorthoester, Orthoester, Vinyl ether, Phosphoramidate,

Hydrazone, b-thiopropionate. (Romberg et al. 2008) The DSPE-PEG coating is commonly used for constructing pH-sensitive liposomes. (Hong et al. 2002; Simoes et al. 2001; Slepishkin et al. 1997) The feature of pH-dependent release is determined by DOPE/CHEMS ratio and PEG percentage. When DSPE-PEG is anchored on to pH-sensitive liposome with a proper molar ratio, it may be randomly extracted and shed from liposome surface allowing uptake by cells when its anchor, the base lipid, becomes unstable in low pH environment. The fusogenic property of DOPE lipid (Boomer et al. 2009; Hatakeyama et al. 2009) may work synergically with TAT peptide to initiate internalization and intracellular delivery. The methodologies for construction and purification of DSPE-PEG-coated nanoliposomes have been well established. (Liang et al. 2004).

Functional peptides

Functional peptides for nanoliposomes can be classified into three categories: 1). cell-penetrating peptides (CPPs); 2). pH-dependent fusion peptides; and 3). special function peptides. Here we just list the names of these peptides. More detailed and condensed information is available in related review papers (Deshayes et al. 2005; Drummond et al. 2000). CPPs include TAT, octarginine/R8, penetratin/ AntpHD, FGF/MTS, VP22, PEP-1, DynA, transportan, MAP, pegelin/SynB, pVEC, KALA, ppTG20, P1, MPG, trimer, and PrP. pH-dependent peptides and toxins include HA2, E1, G1/G2, G, E, gp36, TH8/TH9, GALA, SFP, Poly(Glu-Aiba-Leu-Aib, EGLA-I, EGLA-II, JTS1, VP-1, INF3, INF5, INF7, INF8, INF9, INF10, HA peptide, D4, E5, E5L, E5NN, E5CC, E5P, E5CN, AcE4K, poly(L-lysine), poly(L-histidine), poly(acrylic acid) derivatives, succinylated poly(glycidol)s, and copolymers of N-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM). It may be practical to use CHEMS for titrating nanoliposomes to a desired pH-sensitivity and leave these pH-sensitive peptides as alternative approaches. Lysosomes-disrupting peptides have been reported to enhance intracellular delivery efficiency (Baru et al. 1998). Stroke-homing peptide is a special peptide that has been reported recently being able to targeting ischemic brain tissue. This peptide has the sequence "CLEVSRKNC"

TAT peptide targeted pH-sensitive nanoliposomes for BBB transduction. The human immunodeficiency virus-type 1 trans-activating transcriptional activator (HIV-1 TAT protein, an 86-mer polypeptide) (Frankel and Pabo 1988; Green and Loewenstein 1988) has been shown the ability for inducing cell transduction. Certain small regions of such proteins (10–16-mers) called protein transduction domains (PTDs) are responsible for TAT protein induced cell transduction. The minimal PTD of the TAT protein comprises 11 amino acids (Tyr-Gly-Arg-Lys-Lys-Arg-Arg-Gln-Arg-

Arg-Arg) functioning as a cell penetrating peptides (CPP). Fluorescently labeled TAT was visible throughout the brain 20 minutes after intraperitoneal (IP) administration in mice (Schwarze et al. 1999). Many other CPPs have also been discovered and synthesized (Deshayes et al. 2005). TAT peptide is the most widely used CPP among other CPPs for enhancing BBB penetration and for intracellular drug delivery (Herve et al. 2008). Moreover, relatively large 200-nm plain or polyethylene glycol-coated (PEGylated) nanoliposomes can be delivered into various cells by multiple TAT peptide molecules attached to the nanoliposome surface. (Hyndman et al. 2004; Levchenko et al. 2003; Torchilin 2002; Torchilin et al. 2001)

Stroke-homing peptide. Recently, the CLEVSRKNC (single letter sequence for Cys-Leu-Glu-Val-Ser-Arg-Lys-Asn-Cys) peptide has been demonstrated to be selective for ischemic brain tissue. (Hong et al. 2008) This peptide was screened from a phage peptide library based on a T7 415-1b phage vector displaying CX7C (C, cysteine; X, random peptides) (Pasqualini and Ruoslahti 1996). The CLEVSRKNC-phage preferentially targeted ischemic stroke tissue after intravenous administration in a rat MCA occlusion model. Because the CLEVSRKNC peptide is displayed on the phage membrane, theoretically it should be compatible with nanoliposome membrane layers. This means that CLEVSRKNC peptide may be incorporated onto nanoliposomes layers in ways similar to TAT peptide (Hyndman et al. 2004; Levchenko et al. 2003; Torchilin 2002; Torchilin et al. 2001) for localized drug delivery to ischemic brain tissue.

Lipid and peptide tracers

Lipids and peptides can be conjugated with some fluorescent dye to trace the distribution of nanoliposomes in cells or tissue. Rhodamine and Tetramethyl Rhodamine (TRITC) are commonly used for this purpose, and the synthesis and conjugating process are commercially available.

Liposome size for penumbra drug delivery

Liposome size is one of the factors that influence *in vivo* liposome distribution and drug delivery. The *in vivo* extracellular space width in rat brain is estimated 38-64 nm (Thorne and Nicholson 2006), at least 2-fold greater than estimates from fixed tissue. Liposomes for brain drug delivery have been used in sizes of 50-150 nm (Chapat et al. 1991; Madhankumar et al. 2009), 64-73 nm (Xie et al. 2005), 120-147 nm (Puisieux et al. 1994), and 134-143 nm (Ko et al. 2009). Some of these liposomes sizes were bigger than extracellular space width. In such case, liposomes may mainly depend on endocytosis and transcellular route for drug delivery, similar to the me-

chanism that allows their passage through the BBB (Patel et al. 2009). Because of the shrinkage of extracellular space (Thorne and Nicholson 2006; Zoromba et al. 2008), relatively small-sized liposomes may facilitate interstitial diffusion in ischemic tissue; but a smaller size also increases the risk of potential pulmonary toxicity (Nel et al. 2006).

6. Concluding remarks

The inability to selectively deliver therapeutic agents to brain tissue, especially during ischemic, has been a limitation in the treatment of stroke. However, advanced drug delivery tools provide a me-

chanism to overcome these difficulties in stroke therapy. Because ischemia causes an acidic environment and residual blood flow exists in ischemic penumbral region, liposomal delivery system with a low pH-dependent release feature can be used for targeting ischemic penumbra. The DOPE/CHEMS/DSPE-PEG system holds promises as a basic formula of pH-dependent liposomes for stroke treatment. Other peptides, such as TATp and stroke homing peptide (STROKEp) may provide added features for such system. The proposed working mechanism is depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig.1 Diagram of selective drug delivery to ischemic penumbra by pH-sensitive liposomes. TAT peptide (TATp) and stroke-homing peptide (STROKEp) are conjugated with PEG-PE on the surface of liposomes (TATp-PEG-PE and STROKEp-PEG-PE, respectively). TATp and the lipid layer facilitate drug-loaded liposome passage of the BBB and arrival at interstitial space. Liposomes remain stable in neutral pH environment, but they become destabilized in ischemic region due to low pH. STROKEp helps liposomes targeting ischemic cells. TATp and lipid layer help liposomes uptake by ischemic cells and escaping from endosomes. Destabilized pH-sensitive liposomes release drugs in the cytosol of ischemic cells. A portion of liposomes may release drugs in extracellular space.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by NIH grant 7R21NS065912-02, 5T32NS051147-02 and NS 21076-24.

Conflict of interest

None

References

- Abulrob A, Brunette E, Slinn J, Baumann E, Stanimirovic D. (2008) Dynamic analysis of the blood-brain barrier disruption in experimental stroke using time domain in vivo fluorescence imaging. *Mol Imaging* 7:248-262
- Allen TM. (1994) Long-circulating (sterically stabilized) liposomes for targeted drug delivery. *Trends Pharmacol Sci* 15:215-220
- Allen TM, Hansen C, Martin F, Redemann C, Yau-Young A. (1991) Liposomes containing synthetic lipid derivatives of poly(ethylene glycol) show prolonged circulation half-lives in vivo. *Biochim Biophys Acta* 1066:29-36
- Anderson RE, Tan WK, Meyer FB. (1999) Brain acidosis, cerebral blood flow, capillary bed density, and mitochondrial function in the ischemic penumbra. *J Stroke Cerebrovasc Dis* 8:368-379
- Astrup J, Siesjo BK, Symon L. (1981) Thresholds in cerebral ischemia - the ischemic penumbra. *Stroke* 12:723-725
- Baru M, Nahum O, Jaaro H, Sha'anani J, Nur I. (1998) Lysosome-disrupting peptide increases the efficiency of in-vivo gene transfer by liposome-encapsulated DNA. *J Drug Target* 6:191-199
- Bazzoni G, Dejana E. (2004) Endothelial cell-to-cell junctions: molecular organization and role in vascular homeostasis. *Physiol Rev* 84:869-901
- Beduneau A, Saulnier P, Benoit JP. (2007) Active targeting of brain tumors using nanocarriers. *Biomaterials* 28:4947-4967
- Blume G, Cevc G. (1990) Liposomes for the sustained drug release in vivo. *Biochim Biophys Acta* 1029:91-97
- Blume G, Cevc G. (1993) Molecular mechanism of the lipid vesicle longevity in vivo. *Biochim Biophys Acta* 1146:157-168
- Boomer JA, Qualls MM, Inerowicz HD, Haynes RH, Patri VS, Kim JM, Thompson DH. (2009) Cytoplasmic delivery of liposomal contents mediated by an acid-labile cholesterol-vinyl ether-PEG conjugate. *Bioconjug Chem* 20:47-59
- Chapat S, Frey V, Claperon N, Bouchaud C, Puisieux F, Couvreur P, Rossignol P, Delattre J. (1991) Efficiency of liposomal ATP in cerebral ischemia: bioavailability features. *Brain Res Bull* 26:339-342
- Chen H, Tang L, Qin Y, Yin Y, Tang J, Tang W, Sun X, Zhang Z, Liu J, He Q. (2010) Lactoferrin-modified pro-cationic liposomes as a novel drug carrier for brain delivery. *Eur J Pharm Sci* 40:94-102
- Collins D, Maxfield F, Huang L. (1989) Immunoliposomes with different acid sensitivities as probes for the cellular endocytic pathway. *Biochim Biophys Acta* 987:47-55
- Costin GE, Trif M, Nichita N, Dwek RA, Petrescu SM. (2002) pH-sensitive liposomes are efficient carriers for endoplasmic reticulum-targeted drugs in mouse melanoma cells. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun* 293:918-923
- Cowens JW, Creaven PJ, Greco WR, Brenner DE, Tung Y, Ostro M, Pilkiewicz F, Ginsberg R, Petrelli N. (1993) Initial clinical (phase I) trial of TLC D-99 (doxorubicin encapsulated in liposomes). *Cancer Res* 53:2796-2802
- Deshayes S, Morris MC, Divita G, Heitz F. (2005) Cell-penetrating peptides: tools for intracellular delivery of therapeutics. *Cell Mol Life Sci* 62:1839-1849
- Drummond DC, Zignani M, Leroux J. (2000) Current status of pH-sensitive liposomes in drug delivery. *Prog Lipid Res* 39:409-460
- Ebinger M, De Silva DA, Christensen S, Parsons MW, Markus R, Donnan GA, Davis SM. (2009) Imaging the penumbra - strategies to detect tissue at risk after ischemic stroke. *J Clin Neurosci* 16:178-187
- Emerich DF, Tracy MA, Ward KL, Figueiredo M, Qian R, Henschel C, Bartus RT. (1999) Biocompatibility of poly (DL-lactide-co-glycolide) microspheres implanted into the brain. *Cell Transplant* 8:47-58
- Esneault E, Castagne V, Moser P, Bonny C, Bernaudin M. (2008) D-JNKi, a peptide inhibitor of c-Jun N-terminal kinase, promotes functional recovery after transient focal cerebral ischemia in rats. *Neuroscience* 152:308-320
- Eum WS, Kim DW, Hwang IK, Yoo KY, Kang TC, Jang SH, Choi HS, Choi SH, Kim YH, Kim SY, Kwon HY, Kang JH, Kwon OS, Cho SW, Lee KS, Park J, Won MH, Choi SY. (2004) In vivo protein transduction: biologically active intact pep-1-superoxide dismutase fusion protein efficiently protects against ischemic insult. *Free Radic Biol Med* 37:1656-1669
- Fan YF, Lu CZ, Xie J, Zhao YX, Yang GY. (2006) Apoptosis inhibition in ischemic brain by intraperitoneal PTD-BIR3-RING (XIAP). *Neurochem Int* 48:50-59
- Frankel AD, Pabo CO. (1988) Cellular uptake of the tat protein from human immunodeficiency virus. *Cell* 55:1189-1193
- Green M, Loewenstein PM. (1988) Autonomous functional domains of chemically synthesized human immunodeficiency virus tat trans-activator protein. *Cell* 55:1179-1188
- Grieb P, Forster RE, Strome D, Goodwin CW, Pape PC. (1985) O₂ exchange between blood and brain tissues studied with ¹⁸O₂ indicator-dilution technique. *J Appl Physiol* 58:1929-1941
- Hatakeyama H, Ito E, Akita H, Oishi M, Nagasaki Y, Futaki S, Harashima H. (2009) A pH-sensitive fusogenic peptide facilitates endosomal escape and greatly enhances the gene silencing of siRNA-containing nanoparticles in vitro and in vivo. *J Control Release* 139:127-132
- Hellstrom M, Gerhardt H, Kalen M, Li X, Eriksson U, Wolburg H, Betsholtz C. (2001) Lack of pericytes leads to endothelial hyperplasia and abnormal vascular morphogenesis. *J Cell Biol* 153:543-553

- Herve F, Ghinea N, Scherrmann JM. (2008) CNS delivery via adsorptive transcytosis. *Aaps J* 10:455-472
- Homola A, Zoremba N, Slais K, Kuhlen R, Sykova E. (2006) Changes in diffusion parameters, energy-related metabolites and glutamate in the rat cortex after transient hypoxia/ischemia. *Neurosci Lett* 404:137-142
- Hong HY, Choi JS, Kim YJ, Lee HY, Kwak W, Yoo J, Lee JT, Kwon TH, Kim IS, Han HS, Lee BH. (2008) Detection of apoptosis in a rat model of focal cerebral ischemia using a homing peptide selected from in vivo phage display. *J Control Release* 131:167-172
- Hyndman L, Lemoine JL, Huang L, Porteous DJ, Boyd AC, Nan X. (2004) HIV-1 Tat protein transduction domain peptide facilitates gene transfer in combination with cationic liposomes. *J Control Release* 99:435-444
- Jain KK. (2007) Nanobiotechnology-based drug delivery to the central nervous system. *Neurodegener Dis* 4:287-291
- Kacem K, Lacombe P, Seylaz J, Bonvento G. (1998) Structural organization of the perivascular astrocyte endfeet and their relationship with the endothelial glucose transporter: a confocal microscopy study. *Glia* 23:1-10
- Kastrup A, Engelhorn T, Beaulieu C, de Crespigny A, Moseley ME. (1999) Dynamics of cerebral injury, perfusion, and blood-brain barrier changes after temporary and permanent middle cerebral artery occlusion in the rat. *J Neurol Sci* 166:91-99
- Kaufmann AM, Cardoso ER. (1992) Aggravation of vasogenic cerebral edema by multiple-dose mannitol. *J Neurosurg* 77:584-589
- Klibanov AL, Maruyama K, Torchilin VP, Huang L. (1990) Amphipathic polyethyleneglycols effectively prolong the circulation time of liposomes. *FEBS Lett* 268:235-237
- Kniesel U, Wolburg H. (2000) Tight junctions of the blood-brain barrier. *Cell Mol Neurobiol* 20:57-76
- Ko YT, Bhattacharya R, Bickel U. (2009) Liposome encapsulated polyethylenimine/ODN polyplexes for brain targeting. *J Control Release* 133:230-237
- Latour LL, Kang DW, Ezzeddine MA, Chalela JA, Warach S. (2004) Early blood-brain barrier disruption in human focal brain ischemia. *Ann Neurol* 56:468-477
- Lee HJ, Engelhardt B, Lesley J, Bickel U, Pardridge WM. (2000) Targeting rat anti-mouse transferrin receptor monoclonal antibodies through blood-brain barrier in mouse. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther* 292:1048-1052
- Levchenko TS, Rammohan R, Volodina N, Torchilin VP. (2003) Tat peptide-mediated intracellular delivery of liposomes. *Methods Enzymol* 372:339-349
- Levin VA. (1980) Relationship of octanol/water partition coefficient and molecular weight to rat brain capillary permeability. *J Med Chem* 23:682-684
- Liang W, Levchenko TS, Torchilin VP. (2004) Encapsulation of ATP into liposomes by different methods: optimization of the procedure. *J Microencapsul* 21:251-261
- Madhankumar AB, Slagle-Webb B, Wang X, Yang QX, Antonetti DA, Miller PA, Sheehan JM, Connor JR. (2009) Efficacy of interleukin-13 receptor-targeted liposomal doxorubicin in the intracranial brain tumor model. *Mol Cancer Ther* 8:648-654
- Maioriello AV, Chaljub G, Nauta HJ, Lacroix M. (2002) Chemical shift imaging of mannitol in acute cerebral ischemia. Case report. *J Neurosurg* 97:687-691
- Markoutsas E, Pampalakis G, Niarakis A, Romero IA, Weksler B, Couraud PO, Antimisiaris SG. (2011) Uptake and permeability studies of BBB-targeting immunoliposomes using the hCMEC/D3 cell line. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm* 77:265-274
- Memezawa H, Minamisawa H, Smith ML, Siesjo BK. (1992) Ischemic penumbra in a model of reversible middle cerebral artery occlusion in the rat. *Exp Brain Res* 89:67-78
- Murphy BD, Fox AJ, Lee DH, Sahlas DJ, Black SE, Hogan MJ, Coutts SB, Demchuk AM, Goyal M, Aviv RI, Symons S, Gulka IB, Beletsky V, Pelz D, Hachinski V, Chan R, Lee TY. (2006) Identification of penumbra and infarct in acute ischemic stroke using computed tomography perfusion-derived blood flow and blood volume measurements. *Stroke* 37:1771-1777
- Nedergaard M, Kraig RP, Tanabe J, Pulsinelli WA. (1991) Dynamics of interstitial and intracellular pH in evolving brain infarct. *Am J Physiol* 260:R581-588
- Nel A, Xia T, Madler L, Li N. (2006) Toxic potential of materials at the nanolevel. *Science* 311:622-627
- Ohashi M, Tsuji A, Kaneko M, Matsuda M. (2005) Threshold of regional cerebral blood flow for infarction in patients with acute cerebral ischemia. *J Neuroradiol* 32:337-341
- Ohtsuki S, Terasaki T. (2007) Contribution of carrier-mediated transport systems to the blood-brain barrier as a supporting and protecting interface for the brain; importance for CNS drug discovery and development. *Pharm Res* 24:1745-1758
- Pardridge WM. (1999) Blood-brain barrier biology and methodology. *J Neurovirol* 5:556-569
- Pardridge WM. (2005) The blood-brain barrier: bottleneck in brain drug development. *NeuroRx* 2:3-14
- Pasqualini R, Ruoslahti E. (1996) Organ targeting in vivo using phage display peptide libraries. *Nature* 380:364-366
- Patel MM, Goyal BR, Bhadada SV, Bhatt JS, Amin AF. (2009) Getting into the brain: approaches to enhance brain drug delivery. *CNS Drugs* 23:35-58
- Puisieux F, Fattal E, Lahiani M, Auger J, Jouannet P, Couvreur P, Delattre J. (1994) Liposomes, an interesting tool to deliver a bioenergetic substrate (ATP), in vitro and in vivo studies. *J Drug Target* 2:443-448

- Rahman A, Treat J, Roh JK, Potkul LA, Alvord WG, Forst D, Woolley PV. (1990) A phase I clinical trial and pharmacokinetic evaluation of liposome-encapsulated doxorubicin. *J Clin Oncol* 8:1093-1100
- Rajkumar K, Barron D, Lewitt MS, Murphy LJ. (1995) Growth retardation and hyperglycemia in insulin-like growth factor binding protein-1 transgenic mice. *Endocrinology* 136:4029-4034
- Romberg B, Hennink WE, Storm G. (2008) Sheddable coatings for long-circulating nanoparticles. *Pharm Res* 25:55-71
- Rosenberg GA, Estrada EY, Dencoff JE. (1998) Matrix metalloproteinases and TIMPs are associated with blood-brain barrier opening after reperfusion in rat brain. *Stroke* 29:2189-2195
- Sawant RM, Hurley JP, Salmaso S, Kale A, Tolcheva E, Levchenko TS, Torchilin VP. (2006) "SMART" drug delivery systems: double-targeted pH-responsive pharmaceutical nanocarriers. *Bioconjug Chem* 17:943-949
- Schulze C, Firth JA. (1993) Immunohistochemical localization of adherens junction components in blood-brain barrier microvessels of the rat. *J Cell Sci* 104 (Pt 3):773-782
- Schwarze SR, Ho A, Vocero-Akbani A, Dowdy SF. (1999) In vivo protein transduction: delivery of a biologically active protein into the mouse. *Science* 285:1569-1572
- Shinohara M, Dollinger B, Brown G, Rapoport S, Sokoloff L. (1979) Cerebral glucose utilization: local changes during and after recovery from spreading cortical depression. *Science* 203:188-190
- Siegal T, Rubinstein R, Bokstein F, Schwartz A, Lossos A, Shalom E, Chisin R, Gomori JM. (2000) In vivo assessment of the window of barrier opening after osmotic blood-brain barrier disruption in humans. *J Neurosurg* 92:599-605
- Tamai I, Tsuji A. (2000) Transporter-mediated permeation of drugs across the blood-brain barrier. *J Pharm Sci* 89:1371-1388
- Tamaru M, Akita H, Fujiwara T, Kajimoto K, Harashima H. (2010) Leptin-derived peptide, a targeting ligand for mouse brain-derived endothelial cells via macropinocytosis. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun* 394:587-592
- Thorne RG, Nicholson C. (2006) In vivo diffusion analysis with quantum dots and dextrans predicts the width of brain extracellular space. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 103:5567-5572
- Tiwari SB, Amiji MM. (2006) A review of nanocarrier-based CNS delivery systems. *Curr Drug Deliv* 3:219-232
- Torchilin VP. (2002) TAT peptide-modified liposomes for intracellular delivery of drugs and DNA. *Cell Mol Biol Lett* 7:265-267
- Torchilin VP, Omelyanenko VG, Papisov MI, Bogdanov AA, Jr., Trubetskoy VS, Herron JN, Gentry CA. (1994) Poly(ethylene glycol) on the liposome surface: on the mechanism of polymer-coated liposome longevity. *Biochim Biophys Acta* 1195:11-20
- Torchilin VP, Rammohan R, Weissig V, Levchenko TS. (2001) TAT peptide on the surface of liposomes affords their efficient intracellular delivery even at low temperature and in the presence of metabolic inhibitors. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 98:8786-8791
- Tsuji A. (2005) Small molecular drug transfer across the blood-brain barrier via carrier-mediated transport systems. *NeuroRx* 2:54-62
- Wong HL, Chattopadhyay N, Wu XY, Bendayan R. (2010) Nanotechnology applications for improved delivery of antiretroviral drugs to the brain. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev* 62:503-517
- Xie Y, Ye L, Zhang X, Cui W, Lou J, Nagai T, Hou X. (2005) Transport of nerve growth factor encapsulated into liposomes across the blood-brain barrier: in vitro and in vivo studies. *J Control Release* 105:106-119
- Zlotnik A, Gruenbaum SE, Artru AA, Leibovitz A, Shapira Y. (2008) The Position of Arterial Line Significantly Influences Neurological Assessment in Rats. *ASA Annual Meeting Abstract* 109:A486
- Zoremba N, Homola A, Slais K, Vorisek I, Rossaint R, Lehmenkuhler A, Sykova E. (2008) Extracellular diffusion parameters in the rat somatosensory cortex during recovery from transient global ischemia/hypoxia. *J Cereb Blood Flow Metab* 28:1665-1673